

Connecting the Global Women in Crop Science community - Part II

Report from Global Coffee Mornings held during the week of 20-24th of March 2023

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Background

After the success of the first series of global Women in Crop Science coffee mornings held during September 2022, we organized a second global event series during the week of 20-24th March 2023. This had the same intention: to bring together women working in Crop Science!

This time we had 20 hosts from 14 different countries organizing a local event within their organization, institution, or university. This report summarizes some of the discussions and recommendations from the coffee mornings.

Based on the success of the first two events we have planning another edition:

Save the date: **week of 25-29th September 2023!**

CIMMYT Nairobi, ICRAF Campus, Nairobi (Kenya)

Date: Tuesday 28 March 2023

Host: Pauline Muindi

Place: ICRAF Campus, CIMMYT Summer House, Nairobi, Kenya

Number of Participants: 15

Format: Informal shared lunch with colleagues

Main topics discussed:

We organized a catch-up lunch break with the women working at CIMMYT on Tuesday, March 28th, 2023, outside Summer House, ICRAF campus. We had a chance to introduce ourselves to the new female staff who joined CIMMYT in the past 6 months. I briefly shared the role of Women in Crop Science (WiCS) and how it intends to create spaces where women working in research organizations can come together and share some work experiences, learn from each other, have some laughs, and get to know each other better. Colleagues that visited Mexico for CIMMYT's Science and Innovation Week 2023, stated one of the key messages from the meeting was that ALL CIMMYT's staff play an integral role in achieving CIMMYT's mission and goals. The group suggested that we organize such lunch events every so often to continue to get to know each other, share work updates and unwind!

CIMMYT, Inifap & PIEAES, Ciudad Obregón (Mexico)

Date: Wednesday 22 March 2023

Hosts: Araceli Torres and the WiCS Obregón team (CIMMYT, Inifap & PIEAES)

Place: CENEB, Auditorium Hans J. Braun (Training building)

Number of Participants: 50 participants including visitors of several international institutions that were participating in Wheat Visitors' Week.

Format: After a brief introduction by the hosts, participants were free to mingle and get to know each other.

Main topics discussed:

Presentation and summary of activities of the WiCS team in Obregón, Sonora.

The introduction of the WiCS team at CIMMYT Obregón, included the following central points:

- **Who we are:**

We are a multidisciplinary team of 19 women working in crop science from three institutions on the same campus: CIMMYT; Inifap, which is the national research institution for agricultural, forestry and livestock sciences, and the local organization of farmers that supports research, PIEAES.

- **The work structure is based on an activities committee:**

- Links with the WiCS movement in Batán: Araceli Torres, Virginia Ordóñez, Nayeli Quiche.
- Dissemination of the movement at the local level: Jazmin Rodríguez (CIMMYT), Gabriela Chávez (INIFAP), Rocío Bringas (PIEAES)
- Meeting Logistics: Ana Rosa García (CIMMYT), Fannie Parra (INIFAP), Claudia Leyva (PIEAES)
- Secretary, Drafting of meeting minutes: Ana Laura González, María Elena Cárdenas (CIMMYT), Arely Urias (PIEAES)

- **Support tools:**

WhatsApp group, email, economic contribution to have a fund for coffee, cookies, water for the meetings.

- **Activities:**

Five coffee morning meetings have been organized, which have been developed in different places to better understand our workplaces. In addition, two events were held; the first related to the prevention of violence against women, taught by the Sonoran Institute for Women in Cajeme, Obregón. The second was on personal growth in which a large number of men and women participated and showed great openness and interest in the topic.

- **Achievements:**

WiCS has enabled a uniting of staff across the three institutions in this network, including creating visibility among us and providing the opportunity to do things for the common good. This has included requesting the opening and/or authorization of new toilets for women since the needs in the institutions have changed given the increase in the female population working on this campus. Presenting this summary of activities to visitors is also an achievement for the team, which in this way has the opportunity of being seen off campus. The successes so far help to motivate the team to continue working together.

- **Future plans:**

Continue consolidating and strengthening the team; this is just the beginning of something that will be as big as its members want it to be.

Read a recent "Women in Crop Science Conversation" interview with Araceli Torres here:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7833594>

University of the Philippines Los Baños, Los Baños (Philippines)

Date: Thursday 23 March 2023

Hosts: Dara Realin Fabro & Lenie A. Quiatchon-Baeza

People who helped organizing the event: Seminar Committee headed by Reniel s. Pamplona and Engr. Claire P. Sandro

Place: Edible Landscaping Rm204, Institute of Crop Science-College of Agriculture and Food Science, University of the Philippines Los Baños, Laguna Philippines

Number of Participants: 25

Format: Open discussion forum

Some topics discussed:

1. What or who inspired them to pursue a career in crop science?
2. What are the challenges they faced as a woman in crop science?
3. How did they keep their work-life balance?
4. Any inspirational message to the youth who might be interested in pursuing a career in crop science.

The key takeaways from the event

1. We have come so far from the time when job hiring for crop Science had gender bias for male applicants.
2. Women can and do adopt to perform multiple roles by wearing different hats depending on the most pressing concern at the moment.

Speakers/Focal persons: Eureka M. De Ocampo, PhD, Lucille Elna De Guzman, PhD, Tonette P. Laude, PhD, Kim Nyka Perdiguerra, PhD

The ARC Training Centre for Future Crops Development, Canberra (Australia)

Date: Tuesday 21 March 2023

Hosts: Lauren DuFall and Julie Leroux

Place: Australian National University

Number of Participants: +/- 25

Format: A few groups discussions, open questions about mentoring

Main topics discussed:

A discussion on mentorship focusing on women in crop science was held over coffee at the ANU with Centre fellows, students and colleagues from the Centre for Entrepreneurial Agri-Technology (CEAT). Many shared their experiences of having a number of informal mentors across their careers who played significant roles in supporting awareness of their own strengths, encouraged them to go for new opportunities or awards and introducing them to others in their network to build new connections. Sharing of experiences is an important way that enables people to draw on the experiences of others when they encounter new challenges. The importance of peer-to-peer mentoring was also highlighted, and we have unique opportunities within the Centre to build a culture of mentorship that will harness the value of the diverse experiences and knowledge that exists amongst our cohort.

International Potato Center (CIP), Lima (Peru)

Date: Wednesday 22 March 2023

Hosts: Hannele Lindqvist-Kreuze, Viviana Infantas, Andrea Prado and Jose Torres

Place: CIP HQ La Molina, Lima, Peru

Number of Participants: 30

Format: Casual get together, people brought cakes and drinks to share.

Main topics discussed:

It was a much-appreciated event, and we agreed to continue getting together every two months!

Wageningen University, Wageningen (The Netherlands)

Date: Monday 20th March 2023

Hosts: Katharina Huntenburg and Katharina Hanika

Place: Wageningen Uni Campus

Number of Participants: ca 20 participants (female and male)

Format: 2 flash talks from women in senior positions talking about their way into these positions, their problems along the way and reasons why they stayed in science, with an open discussion afterwards.

Main topics discussed: It is still important to talk about the gender differences, we need allies to change something, and people are happy that events like this are happening. Future events of a similar format would be appreciated.

USDA-ARS Edward T. Schafer Agricultural Center, Fargo (USA)

Date: Wednesday 22 March 2023

Hosts: Katherine Running and Amanda Peters Haugrud

Place: USDA-ARS Edward T. Schafer Agricultural Center in Fargo, ND

Number of Participants: 8

Format: Open discussion and a chance for people to meet each other because there have been only a couple in person events at our center since the pandemic.

Durham University, Durham (UK)

Date: Thursday 23rd March

Host: Jo Hepworth

Place: Durham University

Number of Participants: 5

Format: Low key event. The discussions highlighted that it would be good to work on mentorship for the earlier career members.

UK Monogram Network meeting, Reading (UK)

Date: Tuesday 4 April 2023

Hosts: The UK Monogram Network (bringing together the UK's cereals and grasses community) Women in Crop Science Coffee morning was hosted by Stéphanie Swarbreck and Laura Dixon as part of the Monogram Conference held at the University of Reading and organized by Dr Paola Tosi.

Place: Reading University, Reading, UK

Number of Participants: 40+

Format: The format was to initially let the participants discuss amongst themselves and network and then we had a mini session on mentoring where we talked about what mentoring is and how to get what you need from it. Then we invited participants to think about their mentoring needs and discuss this with others in groups of 2-3 people.

We made sure we had a board /post-it notes and asked 2 questions:

1. What does mentoring mean to you?
2. And the other more specific to the monogram community: How can the Monogram community support you?

Key takeaways:

These are the post-it note comments off the board at the end of the session:

- Add gender pro-nouns to name badges.
- More representation for non-wheat crops (at the overall Monogram meeting).
- Next time hopefully not at 8am. Plan events for friendly times of day!
- Mentorship is greatly needed for the early career/postdoc transition upwards.
- Feeling seen and heard is important: knowing your questions are not being dismissed.
- Career advice from a range of sources is useful.

CIMMYT, Harare (Zimbabwe)

Date: Friday 24 March 2023

Hosts: CIMMYT Southern Africa Regional Office funded the event, hosted by Shiela Chikulo, Catherine Magada, Pamela Chirwa and Esnath Hamadziripi.

Place: Vanilla Moon Restaurant, Harare

Number of Participants: 29 women including representatives from: CIMMYT Administration, CIMMYT research assistants, CIMMYT scientists, CIMMYT partners from seed companies and government research institutions.

Format: The event took an open conversation/dialogue format.

- Welcome remarks (2min).
- Introductions (30 min): Each woman introduced themselves freely to the extent of what they wanted people to know. Most shared number of children, marital status and what they do at work whether its supporting scientific work or some exciting technical aspect of their daily activities in the field.
- Teas and pictures (30min): The participants enjoyed a coffee buffet where one could select teas, coffee and eats.
- Table discussion (40min): A discussion topic was placed at the center of each table prior to the meeting. As participants sat down with the tea, they discussed the topic placed at their tables. Then one representative from each group shared the main points that came out of the discussion and another would share any personal testimony applicable to the topic. Topics discussed included: mentorship, work-life balance, career development and elevating women's voices.
- Closing: Vote of thanks and pictures were taken at the end of the meeting!

Main topics discussed:

- The women in attendance were thankful for this initiative and keen to have more in the future.
- Women who wear many hats of wife, mum and work shared the challenges and the importance of having a work-life balance.
- There was a deep sense of gratitude for women who have helped and supported other women to achieve their goals in various capacities in mentorship and helping to elevate women's voices.
- Some women's roles go un-noticed and un-appreciated and the event gave women a sense of belonging and that they are appreciated and supported, especially by other women.

International Potato Center (CIP), Kigali (Rwanda)

Date: Friday 24 March 2023

Hosts: The event was hosted by CGIAR in Rwanda and organized by the participating CGIAR staff.

Place: CGIAR offices in Kigali, Rwanda

Number of Participants: 25

Format: Informal coffee break for participants to get to know each other. The guest of honor (Chantal Ingabire, Director General for Planning at the Ministry of Agriculture in Rwanda) prepared a speech on her experience as a professional woman in agriculture in Rwanda. Then others shared their experiences. We also talked about the way forward for creating a longer-term Women in Crop Science community in Rwanda.

Main topics discussed:

- The participants felt there is a need for a community of professional women in agriculture and crop science in Rwanda to empower women in the sector and to encourage more women to join the sector.
- Female professionals in agriculture and crop science in Rwanda face challenges resulting from the fact that they are underrepresented and face numerous social expectations. A community can help to empower women through peer-to-peer support to address these challenges.
- The group is supportive of organizing follow up events (e.g., twice a year) where specific topics can be discussed.
- We decided to create a WhatsApp group for future communication.

McFadden 2023 Symposium, Texas (USA)

Date: Tuesday 25 April 2023

Hosts: Amanda de Oliveira Silva, Mary Gutieri, Katherine Frels, Shannon Baker and Abbey Whipple

Place: Edgar S. McFadden 2023 Symposium in Grapevine, Texas

Number of Participants: 20 (male and female)

Format: Since we were in a small group, we conducted an open discussion about the topic and each person provided their perspective.

Main topics discussed:

We centered our discussion around the topic *“How can Crop Science Cultivate More Strong Female Leads”* (for a review of Arwa Mahdawi’s excellent book of this title see here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6045227>).

Mary Gutieri talked about the book and encouraged everyone to read it.

Susanne Dreisigacker the Wheat Molecular Breeding Laboratory Head at CIMMYT provided a speech regarding her view and experiences. She discussed with the group about the impact of growing up in man-dominated family how that can affect one’s confidence in leading in the future. She believes that empathetic, inclusive, transparent, and collaborative environments could be strategies to cultivate more strong female leads.

In addition, other strategies and comments to cultivate stronger female leads include:

- Using the so-called “impostor syndrome” for good by analyzing the issues that lie behind it. Questions to ask ourselves would be “what is my fear?”; “what do I know and don’t know?” This will enable us to act and feel more confident.
- Women are less likely than men to take risks with things they don’t understand. Finding mentors and collaborators that can help and support your endeavor could help.
- People often see women as less knowledgeable than men in group settings. Men should know how their support, especially in public and man-dominated cultures, can help their female colleagues. It is crucial they “pass the mic” and let people know their women colleagues are the experts in the room when in fact they are.
- Mentoring programs and safe spaces for discussions, like these coffee morning events, are beneficial to empower women in science and in ensuring they feel connected.

